

PURSUIT OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR IN COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT (CAI) AND OPEN HOLE COMPRESSION (OHC)

Takashi Ishikawa^{*}, Yuichiro Aoki^{*} and Hiroshi Suemasu[#]

^{*}: *Advanced Composites Evaluation Technology Center,
Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA)
6-13-1, Ohsawa, Mitaka-shi, Tokyo 181-0065, Japan*

[#]: *Mechanical Engineering Department, Sophia University,
7-1, Kioi-cho, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo 102-8554, Japan 506*

SUMMARY: Compression after Impact (CAI) and Open Hole Compression (OHC) tests often provide the most critical strength data in aircraft composite structure design. Allowable strain limit is mainly decided by these data for composite primary structures and they govern weight reduction ratios of structures by composites application. These tests sometimes are conducted as material screening phase in evaluating new polymer composite system due to matrix polymer dependency. Failure mechanisms of these tests have been pursued and clarified in experimental and theoretical procedures during more than this decade. In CAI behavior, the first clarified process is a response of impact damage revolution. Although experimental knowledge is very popular, high level prediction is still difficult. The authors' group has made a success in high quality numerical prediction. Compression process after impact is also analyzed and correlated with experimental findings. Recent experimental results of CAI behavior of fully moisture saturated CFRP plates are also shown. Findings in the newly started research part, clarification of OHC failure process is also presented.

KEYWORDS: Impact, Delamination, Finite Element, Local Buckling, Damage Propagation, Interlaminar Fracture Toughness, Fibre Micro-buckling

INTRODUCTION

Compression after impact (CAI) tests and open hole compression (OHC) tests are considered as a crucial evaluation in the design process of composite primary structures. Design allowable strain limits of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are mainly defined from CAI or OHC results for composite (CFRP) primary structures and these limit values govern weight reduction ratios. As another aspect of CAI and OHC tests, they are considered to be a material screening parameter for evaluating new composite systems for structural applications. Although CAI tests does not seem to be the best for this purpose, thousands of CAI tests have been conducted in advanced composite material supplier companies. Therefore, necessity of CAI tests is enhanced in both aircraft and composite material industries and deep understanding of mechanics in CAI tests is indispensable background for identification of the governing property of the test results. In some case, OHC tests are also used in the material screening phase because the test cost of OHC is much less than CAI. Thus, deep understanding of the mechanism of OHC failure process is also very important. However,

ambiguity in mechanics of CAI and OHC failure behavior may lead to misunderstanding of test data and to wrong direction in material development.

In order to clarify mechanism of CAI behavior as the first stage, one of the author (TI) and his group started mainly experimental investigations more than a decade ago. This group found some experimental features in CAI behavior [1] and [2] and they will be reviewed here. Findings are basically divided into two phases corresponding to two experimental steps, impact related and compression related. The other author (HS) and his group were consulted by TI for numerical analysis and transferred experimental information from TI's group. They started consecutive numerical analysis modeling each phase of behavior in CAI. Except for very complicated part of the problem, such as delamination propagation near the final failure, his group achieved a great success in numerical explanation of the key points in failure mechanism. Although some portions of their work were already published [3], [4], and [5], it will be quoted again in this review paper and harmonized explanation with experimental results will be given. The latest experimental information about CAI behavior of well moisture-absorbed CFRP laminates is also given in this paper.

The newest portion of research is clarification of mechanism of OHC behavior. This part was started around four years ago after the finding that the modern toughened CF/epoxy does not necessarily show the high OHC strengths. The basic idea is to observe several OHC strength tests at in-situ condition where a fiber optics microscope was used in this case. An approximate scenario to initial local damage to the final failure was identified by these in-situ observations. Some early numerical results based on FEM modeling is also given, although the correlation between experiments and predictions is not as good as CAI cases.

EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS ABOUT CAI: IMPACT PHASE

Series of work about CAI behavior were conducted by one of the authors (TI) and his group belonging to Advanced Composites Evaluation Technology Center (ACE TeC) in Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA: used to be National Aerospace Laboratory, NAL) such as [1], [2], [6], and its very interesting nature was revealed. The findings are divided into two experimental phases: impact and compression. Here, findings related to impact delamination are described first. Figure 1 (left) indicates typical examples of accumulated delamination created by a drop weight impact of 3.3 J/mm for SACMA specimens. The material system for left picture was modern toughened CF/Epoxy (T800/3633 by Toray Co.

Fig. 1: Typical geometry of impact delamination created into CF/Epoxy Laminates
 Left for T800/3633 (Toray, Toughened): Conical shaped, SACMA specimen (32ply, Q.I.)
 Right for KA/ 410 (Mitsubishi Rayon, Conventional and Brittle, 1st Generation): Extreme hat-brim shaped (Magnified), NASA specimen (48ply, Q.I.)

LTD) and this material will be referred later in the chapter of “Experimental findings: Compression phase”. This picture was taken by ACE TeC’s new ultrasonic C-scanner. In CF/epoxy, the accumulated delamination shapes are likely conical or even hat-brim shaped as shown in Figure 1 right. It should be noted that such a hat shape does not always appear for all CF/epoxy’s. So far as performed experiments by the authors concerned, cylindrical or lightly conical accumulated delamination shapes are likely to appear for lower energy cases, thinner specimen, i.e. SACMA method, and tougher material systems. Although quantitative explanations of such geometry cannot be given now, qualitative suggestion is given in later numerical calculation chapter. It should be also noted that the direction of spirals (clockwise or counter-clockwise) changes at the center plane of the laminate if we look at Figure 1 in detail. This phenomenon is a direct reflection of the mirror symmetry of the laminate. Figure 1 (Right) also indicates a schematic view of the accumulated delamination structure hinted by actual picture details. This kind of information about delamination structure was transferred to the second author and his group for setting up the analytical model. Of course, the authors’ group is not necessarily the first people who identify the structure of impact delamination. For examples at early days, the Boeing company team reported [7] the structure of impact delamination and simplified analysis of CAI and EADS (Aerospatiale Co. at that time) people reported [8] a delamination structure and numerical analysis of CAI.

Fig. 2: Relationships between projected delamination area and normalized impact energy by thickness

SACMA STD: Standard supporting fixture in SACMA method using rubber clamp

SACMA PF: Two picture frame Type supporting fixture

NASA: Modified NASA impact through 102mm square window

As the final point of this chapter, Figure 2 indicates relationships between projected delamination area and normalized impact energy by thickness. Legends indicated are related to impact methods and supporting fixtures as explained in the caption. Here, the projection area is defined as the envelope of the largest delamination radii and it should be noted that this projected area is not the total area of delamination. Two important findings are implicitly described in Fig. 2: An existence of impact energy threshold of 1.2 J/mm to create delamination can be found and a leveling-off in delamination area increase is shown. Theoretical prediction of the first finding was given by one of the author (HS) [3] and the present data can be considered as the collateral evidence of this theory. The second finding will be referred as “delamination saturation” later and its mechanism can be easily explained: Delamination edges almost reach the vicinity of impact supporting frames and their further propagation becomes impossible. This delamination saturation will be an important factor for considering the optimum specimen size.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF CAI: IMPACT PHASE

Series of numerical analysis using finite element analyses (FEA) were conducted mainly one of the author's (HS) group. The problem is divided into two phases: explanation of multiple impact delamination shape and buckling/ postbuckling analysis of delaminated plies. Even in the first delamination analysis, the problem is further divided into two steps: a qualitative explanation of delamination shapes in quasi-isotropic laminates and a quantitative analysis for cross-ply laminates including delamination propagation using a specially developed interface element. The phase of impact delamination related studies are explained first where the impact force is always replaced by the static indentation force because the effect of dynamics is quite small in an impact speed range at the actual CAI tests. Figure 3 describes the basic idea of the first step of the first phase analysis of two multiple delamination models [4] in a square laminate of 16 plies $[(-45/90/45/0)_4]$ where Model A does not take an account of a transverse crack in the delaminated circle and where Model B takes an account of such a crack. Energy release rate (ERR) at each delamination front was calculated under a lateral point loading at the delamination center and under fixed boundary conditions along four edges of the plate by the virtual crack closure technique. The used material elastic properties in FEA analysis are as follows: for a CFRP orthotropic lamina, $E_L = 142$ GPa, $E_T = 10.8$ GPa, $G_{LT} = 5.49$ GPa, $G_{TT} = 4.15$ GPa, $\nu_{LT} = \nu_{TL} = 0.3$; for a hypothetical isotropic lamina, $E = 56.5$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$. Figure 4 depicts the FEA model partition in the present analysis by ABAQAS code where used elements are 3D brick of 20 nodes and 3D wedge of 15 nodes at the loading point. Numbers of elements and nodes are 16,000 and 28,000, respectively. Contact phenomena between elements in the delaminated area are handled by a nonlinear spring which is established in the previous studies. Three cases of the delamination diameter of 10, 20 and 30 mm are considered.

Fig. 3: Schematic explanation of multiple delaminations for Energy Release Rate (ERR) calculation by FEA: Square CFRP laminate of 16 plies, $(-45/90/45/0)_4$ stacking sequence.

Fig. 4: FEA model for ERR calculation of multi-delamination square laminate

diameter cases. This trend again coincides qualitatively with an experimental finding that a delamination shape of hat and brim appears likely by high impact energy for brittle composite laminates. More detailed numerical survey will be needed for more quantitative explanation of the experimental behavior in delamination structure.

Fig. 5: Explanation of directional ERR distribution at delamination #1 and #9. Red curve: Difference in elastic modulus at two adjacent lamina (-45 and 90 deg.)

From here on, the second step of the first phase analysis, i.e. the delamination propagation simulation [9] will be explained. In this step, the simulation has been conducted so far for some cross-ply laminates in order to simplify the problem. Thus, some static indentation and impact tests for the cross-ply laminate have been conducted for the better comparison with numerical predictions and the picture of a static test and the results of load-deflection curves will be shown in Fig.7. It can be seen that the load-deflection responses in static and impact tests are quite similar to each other. Figure 8 depicts a comparison of accumulated delamination geometries by static and impact tests where considerable similarity can be found. Hence, the assumption of replacement of an impact load by static one can be justified.

Figure 5 indicates numerical ERR results at delaminations #1 and #9 for orthotropic lamina case of model B with $d=20\text{mm}$ at $P= 2.56\text{kN}$. An outer curve in this figure shows a plot of elastic moduli difference between adjacent lamina, i.e., $E_{90}(\theta) - E_{45}(\theta)$. It can be concluded that ERR directional distribution is somehow close to the modulus difference between adjacent lamina for central delaminations. This finding is qualitatively correlated with a petal-like delamination shape described in Fig. 1. While a presentation is omitted, directional distribution shapes of ERR at each delamination are quite different from an isotropic case. The thickness-wise distribution of the maximum ERR value in the directional distribution is shown in Fig. 6 for CFRP lamina cases of Models A and B. It can be seen that ERR near the bottom surface becomes higher for larger delamination

Fig.6: Thickness-wise distribution of maximum ERR at each delamination for CFRP lamina Model A: open legends, Model B: filled legends Indication by dotted oval: Suggestion of experiments

Fig. 7: (a) Picture of static indentation test for cross-ply laminates
(b) Comparison of load-deflection response in static and impact tests

Fig.8: Record of Ultrasonic C-scan for indicating accumulated delaminations
(a): Static test, (b) Impact test

The core issue of the second step of the first phase, a delamination propagation analysis [9], is explained next. A key theoretical basis developed here is a type of cohesive element for describing the mechanical behavior during delamination propagation. The detail of the idea and analytical procedure will appear in this ICCM-15 paper [10] and be omitted here. Two patterns of model geometries are shown in Fig.9, where the difference is a consideration of matrix cracks. In model (b), obliquely accumulated matrix cracks in the real damage mode

Fig.9: Geometrical models for delamination propagation prediction during lateral loading
(a): Only delaminations considered, (b): Delaminations and matrix cracks considered

Fig.10: Predicted damage growth related behavior in static indentation tests
 (a): Load-deflection relationships, (b): Predicted delamination propagation pattern

are considerably simplified as shown, i.e., as aligned parallel cracks. It should be noted that such matrix cracks also exist in four 0 lamina in Model B. Based on these models, numerical predictions are performed for clarification of the delamination propagation behavior. Typical results are shown in Fig. 10. Figure 10 (a) depicts load-lateral deflection relationships for an intact laminate and Models A and B. Note that the obtained deflection response by Model B is quite similar to the experimental result shown in Fig. 7 (b). Figure 10 (b) depicts the predicted delamination shape by Model B, which is quite close to the experimental pattern shown in Fig.8 (a). In summary, the delamination growth behavior by a lateral force can be well explained by a numerical procedure using the specially developed cohesive interface elements and introducing the modeled matrix cracks. Preliminary experimental results verify that a difference in behavior between static and impact load is quite trivial. This numerical procedure will be expanded soon to a quasi-isotropic laminate containing ± 45 lamina.

EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS ABOUT CAI: COMPRESSION PHASE

Compression tests for delaminated specimens were conducted with central deflection measurement of delamination circle and/or moiré-topography camera equipped. Boundary conditions employed were fixed at loading (top) and supporting (bottom) ends and simply supported at side edges as specified in NASA and SACMA testing methods. Compression loads were introduced by a screw driven testing machine of 500kN capacity with a crosshead speed of 0.2 mm/min. Figure 11 depicts typical stress-central deflection diagrams for NASA specimens of CF/epoxy (conventional, KA/410) and CF/PEEK (APC-2, very tough) cases. A unique behavior captured for CF/epoxy was a quasi-static deflection reverse just before the final collapse failure. A sectional schematic view for explanation of the behavior is shown in Fig.12. At the first stage in post buckling, all delaminated pieces deformed toward the impact direction as indicated in Fig.12 probably due to the initial imperfection. Then, transition of

Fig. 11: Relationships between compressive stress and out-of-plane deflection for CFRP laminates (NASA)

buckling mode, i.e., deflection reverse, occurred just before peak stress (at an arrow in Fig.11). This deflection reverse is related, or triggered by transverse delamination propagation to the compressive loads.

In order to explain such transverse delamination propagation in detail, consecutive moiré topography pictures taken from the other side of impact for CF/epoxy is shown in Fig.13. The fringes indicate the isovalue contour of the out-of-plane deflection and each fringe corresponds to 1.1mm and the percentage shown under each picture indicates the ratio to the maximum load. For the CF/epoxy, the buckling deformation induces a transverse delamination propagation of delamination to the loading direction at 85% load level. Delamination penetration almost throughout the width was captured at 98% load, while the deflection reverse started roughly simultaneously. During the whole process of deflection reverse, the load decreased slightly as observed in Fig. 11. Although the indication is omitted, the complete deflection reverse cannot be

Fig. 12: Schematic sectional views of deflection reverse

Fig.13: Consecutive moiré topography pictures for delaminated CF/epoxy NASA specimen (Percentage: relative load to level to the maximum)

always observed even for KA/410 CF/epoxy. For lower impact energy cases, or for smaller specimen size (i.e. SACMA), the final failure happened before the complete reverse path. However, the tendency moving to the reverse direction is always observed and its partial reason might be ascribed to the dynamic fidelity of the deflection pick-up.

Variation in CAI strengths governed by normalized impact energy by the plate thickness obtained is indicated in Fig. 14 for CF/epoxy (KA/410: conventional) using SACMA and NASA testing methods. This sort of plot is referred as typical “CAI behavior” which is considered in the early phase strength design of aircraft primary structures. It can be seen that two methods provide similar CAI strength properties over 2 J/mm and that some discrepancy is found between 1 and 2 J/mm. To be exact,

Fig. 14: Relationships between normalized impact energy and CAI strengths (KA/410)

SACMA results show more serious drop in CAI strengths than NASA results beyond the impact energy level of delamination threshold.

One of the authors (TI) explored the unified understanding of CAI strength trend obtained by both methods. The current best idea is to plot the CAI data depending on the ratio (R_c) of the diameter of hypothetical cylinder of upper portion of delamination geometry (D_c) to the specimen width (b), i.e. $R_c = D_c/b$. This schematic is shown in Fig. 15 compatible to the ultrasonic images in Fig. 1. If we admit this measure, the plotted results of all CAI data for CF/epoxy (KA/410) indicated in Fig. 14 are modified as Fig.16. This figure depicts a very good accordance in the CAI strengths from both methods. Thus, as long as SACMA and NASA methods, a common way to interpret the CAI strengths could be found. Discrepancy at low energy region can be ascribed to shear instability failure likely happening in thick NASA specimens.

From here on, the latest knowledge about CAI experimental results will be described, which is the effect of well absorbed moisture on CAI behaviour [11]. In this group of experiments, toughened and heat resistant CF/epoxy (Toray T800/3633) was employed as the objective composite. The feature of these experiments is a very long immersion time into hot water ($71 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$), 10,000 hour= more than a year. Figure 17 depicts water absorption history as the function of real time where “experimental” means the measured value using a digital chemical balance and “numerical” means FEM simulation results based on Fick’s theory [12]. Although the detail is ascribed to Ref. 11, the orthotropy in water absorption was introduced into the analysis. A very good correlation between the prediction and experiments can be found and the important point is that 10,000 hour is still not enough for the complete saturation. Impact tests were conducted after this duration immersion and delamination area was measured. Figure 18 compares the projected delamination area which is the envelope of the largest diameters for dry and absorbed specimens. Although water affects the toughening region between each ply of this composite system, the delamination area

Fig. 15: Relationships between Ratio of R_c and CAI strengths for CF/epoxy based on NASA and SACMA methods

Fig. 16: Relationships between Ratio of R_c and CAI strengths for CF/epoxy based on NASA and SACMA methods (KA/410)

Fig. 17. Water absorption history: Experiments and prediction (T800/3633)

Fig. 18. Delamination area (projected) comparison for dry and wet specimens

becomes smaller in the water absorbed specimens. This fact will be the main reason of the important point in the CAI strength results explained later. Figure 19 summarizes the CAI strengths of dry and water-absorbed specimens at various temperature points and indicates reference information of interlaminar fracture toughness taken from JAXA advanced composite database system. Several important findings are indicated in this figure where two or three CAI data are included at each temperature. The first point is that CAI strengths are well correlated with mode II fracture toughness at least from the room to mid-high temperature (121 °C). The second finding is that CAI strengths of wet specimens are slightly higher than those of dry specimens. As suggested above, the delamination area shown in Fig. 18 roughly governs CAI strengths. The third and the most impressive finding is a serious decrease in CAI strength in wet specimen at 177 °C. According to the measurement of the glass transition temperature (T_g), T_g was decreased to 124 °C for the water-absorbed specimen. Thus, the tested temperature for compression is quite high and the compressive strength of the composite was almost lost. Ultrasonic C-scan images taken after compression failure shown in Fig. 20 support the above idea. In the case of 177 °C wet CAI test, delamination accumulation was not the trigger of the failure. Instead, buckling induced crippling type of failure is observed in this case. Such peripheral information of CAI behavior in water absorbed specimens is helpful to understand the overall CAI behavior.

Fig.19: Relationships between CAI strength, interlaminar fracture specimen toughness and temperature (T800/3633)

Fig.20: Ultrasonic C-scan images taken after compression tests at 177 °C (T800/3633)
 (a): dry, (b): Water absorbed

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF CAI: COMPRESSION PHASE

The second phase of the numerical analysis is buckling/postbuckling problem of a laminate with multiple delaminations [13], [14]. This phase is also divided into two steps: analysis without the delamination growth and with the delamination growth. Figure 21 shows a schematic explanation of the analyzed problem where 8 plies and 7 delaminations with different diameters of a truncated cone shape suggested in Fig.1 are considered. Although the real geometry of the delamination shows a helical structure of each ply, it is too complicated to model and 4 ply set is assumed as a delaminated portion. Thus, quasi-isotropy and no bending-extension coupling effect are assumed. A schematic element division and handling of the contact problem are shown in Fig.22. As shown there, the contact problem is handled as a nonlinear spring and, as the first step of the second phase, no delamination growth is introduced. Model names are listed up in Table 1 where mainly diameters of the delamination are varied. Typical load-central deflection curves in this Phase 2, Step1 are shown in Fig. 23 for Model D20-DD. This model symbolizes a hat and brim geometry of delamination indicated in Fig.1. Very important suggestions are indicated in Fig.23: One point is that the total delamination buckling behavior is controlled by the smallest diameter delamination lamina although the largest delamination piece buckles naturally at the lowest load in both cases. The second suggestion is that a trend of deflection reverse is captured in this case although the deflection mode is slightly different from the experiment. Because the transverse delamination growth is not taken into account, a compression load increases after all the delamination portion buckled.

Fig. 21: Schematic of the delamination buckling problem in CAI behavior

20 node isoparametric brick element
 (15 node isoparametric wedge element)
 Approximation of Contact: Spring element (no restraint in tension and very stiff in compression)

Fig. 22: Finite element modeling and approximation of the contact problem

Table 1: Summary of the models

Model	Diameters of Delaminations (mm)
D0	No Delaminations
D20-S	20 × 7
D20-D	12.5,15,17.5,20,22.5,25,27.5
D20-DD	12.5,15,17.5,20,22.5,25,37.5
D30-S	30 × 7
D30-D	22.5,25,27.5,30,32.5,35,37.5
D30-DD	22.5,25,27.5,30,32.5,35,47.5

The next problem is the second step of phase 2, i.e., introduction of the delamination growth. For conducting this step, the cohesive interface element explained in the impact delamination

Fig. 23: Typical load-center displacement curves of delaminated circles in model D20-DD

growth is again used. Description of the theoretical detail is left to Refs.9, 10 and 14. Figure 24 indicates an element arrangement used in this analysis including delamination propagation. Due to the instinct heavy non-linearity of the problem, conditions for convergence are generally not good. Hence, the geometrical size of the problem is reduced from Step 1, e.g., delamination numbers are 3 instead of 7 in no growth case. Table 2 summarizes the nomination of the models. As a typical result, load vs. lateral displacement curves for Model D30-3D are indicated in Fig. 25 where displacement reverse and unstable behaviour is well described. Note that this kind of behaviour is highly initial imperfection sensitive. If we compare this figure with the typical experimental results of Fig.11, the assumed extent of initial imperfection in Fig. 25 may not be enough for a better simulation. The appearing buckling mode in the final analysis phase is rather anti-symmetric and the experimental buckling mode is opening symmetric. The exact reason of buckling mode difference is still ambiguous and further research is needed.

Probably, the most important result in the delamination growth analysis is the description of the maximum load as shown in Fig.26 where PD30-3D means the delamination propagation analysis and D30-3D means the same initial geometry and no growth analysis. No growth simulation and no delamination model behave quite similarly in terms of load vs. end-shortening relationships where loads increase continuously. However, the peak load is captured in the case of delamination growth analysis. Although a sudden load drop is described in this case, in the other cases of different delamination diameters and shapes lead to gradual decrease of loads. It is very clear that the maximum load is always identified in all the tried delamination propagation simulation cases. Figure 27 depicts delamination growth patterns for

Fig. 24: Finite element modeling for delamination growth analysis

Table 2: Summary of the models for delamination growth analysis

Model	Number of Delaminations	Diameters of Delaminations (mm)
D50-1	1	50
D30-3S	3	30
D30-3D	3	25, 30, 35

Fig. 25: Typical load-displacement curves at delaminated circles for model PD30-3D in delamination growth analysis

Fig. 26: Typical load vs. end-shortening curves for no delamination model, no growth analysis and delamination growth analysis

PD30-3D case. In this simulation, the delamination growth takes place just before the peak load. This finding coincides with the experimental findings typified in Fig.11. The very important issue appearing in Fig.27 is the transverse growth of the delamination to the load. This point is the finding in the experiments with no exception. Also in the numerical simulation, no exception is experienced in all the trials. Thus, the main features of the CAI behavior is now almost clarified by these numerical simulations.

Fig. 27: Delamination growth history in Model PD30-3D

EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS ABOUT OHC

As stated earlier, open hole compression strengths (OHC) are another critical values for the design of load bearing composite structures. In some modern toughened composites for higher CAI strength, OHC strengths are sometimes relatively lower than corresponding CAI strengths based on the idea of hypothetical cylinder. However, quite few pieces of research work are reported about clarification of the OHC behavior. So, as the first phase of the present research, experimental in-situ observation during the test was intended by using a fiberoptic microscope with video-recording. As the experimental procedure, the baseline method

Fig. 28: Load-End displacement relations in OHC tests

employed was SACMA 3R-94, one of *de facto* standards of OHC testing. NAL method using shorter specimen and the same width and hole size as SACMA was also employed as the future candidate of standard method. However, detailed explanation about testing methods themselves is skipped here. Typical load-end displacement curves are shown for 2 kinds of CF/epoxy, KA/410 and IM600/QC101 in Fig.28. KA/410 is the same material as stated in previous CAI chapters, 1st generation CF/epoxy, whereas IM600/QC101 is an experimental CF/epoxy system somehow toughened. Figure 29 shows pictures around the hole taken in-situ under compression loading. Load levels when pictures were taken are shown in Fig. 28 by alphabets. It should be noted that fabric patterns found in KA/410 pictures are stenciled by bleeder cloth because this prepreg is a bleeding type and that unidirectional tape lamina is utilized for fabricating this laminate. In both composite systems, fiber micro-buckling in 0 degree lamina (at the second, sixth, eleventh and fifteenth plies) is observed at relatively low load levels (4 – 5 kN). During load increase after initial fiber micro buckling, deformation and quantity of buckled fiber are enlarged and this micro-buckled portion loses load-carrying capability. It could be a trigger of delamination as indicated in Figure 30. Failure processes to the final stage are different in each CF/epoxy material: In KA/410 with high modulus matrix resin, delaminations between the 45, -45 and micro-buckled 0 plies propagate gradually and matrix cracks in the surface 45 become predominant. After observing evolution of internal delaminations between each ply, the final catastrophic failure occurs in this CF/epoxy. In IM600/101 composite system with low neat resin modulus, the surface 45 ply

KA/410 A: Fiber micro buckling B: Matrix crack at surface ply C: Final failure

IM600/101 A: Fiber micro buckling D: Compression failure at surface ply E: Final failure

Fig.29: Pictures of gradual failure processes around a hole in OHC tests for two CF/epoxy systems: KA/410 and IM600/101)

covering the delaminated area starts to buckle in a lamina level and then it shows a compressive failure line orthogonal to the fiber direction (center picture in lower row in Fig.29). Shortly after such surface lamina collapse, internal delamination evolution of large scale can be observed and then the final failure is induced.

Fig.30: Schematic illustration of the initial fiber buckling and delamination onsets in OHC tests

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF OHC: INITIAL STAGE

In order to understand the failure mechanism of OHC tests, numerical simulations based on the knowledge accumulated for CAI explanation have been undertaken in recent years. However, the depth of the understanding is not enough at the present stage. The initial stage results in a fundamental two dimensional analysis are shown in Fig.31 where qualitative explanation of the fiber local buckling in 0-lamina is shown. Later, an improved three dimensional simulation has being conducted based on the idea as shown Fig.32. The first results are shown in Fig.33 and the process

Fig. 31: Preliminary two-dimensional FEM analysis of OHC tests; stress concentration in 0 deg laminae

of damage evolution is not so well explained as the case of CAI. More intensive work will be required in the near future.

Fig.33: Initial numerical results of progressive failure analysis for OHC behavior

Fig. 32: Schematic of progressive failure analysis for explanation of OHC behavior

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are derived for experimental findings and numerical simulations about CAI and OHC behavior of CF/epoxy laminates:

1. Delamination geometry by impact is identified in CAI behavior. It likely tends from a conical to hat-and-brim shape by high energy or for less tough composites and it tends to a cylindrical shape by low energy or for tougher composites.
2. Energy threshold in CAI for creating delaminations is found by experiments, while its theoretical suggestion is obtained by the analysis.
3. Delamination shape in each ply, which is a twin-petal like contour, can be qualitatively explained by the elastic modulus difference between two adjacent lamina containing a delamination. The most serious difference direction coincides with the largest energy release rate, i.e., the largest diameter of the delamination.
4. Delamination propagation simulation under the lateral static force agrees well with experimental results so far for some cross-ply laminates. Theoretical key factors are the developed cohesive interface element and introduction of matrix cracks in each ply.
5. The CAI failure mechanisms are roughly controlled by two factors: Smaller delamination size resulting from high toughness (mainly mode II) increases a local buckling stress of delaminated plies. Higher toughness (mainly mode I) retards the final delamination propagation transverse to loading and increases CAI strength.
6. The CAI strengths obtained by SACMA and NASA methods can be coherently explained by introducing an idea of virtual cylinder and its diameter, D_c .
7. Numerical simulations based on no growth delamination concept can explain well initial stage of multiple delaminations buckling behavior. However, it shows gradual increase of the compression load and does not show the maximum value. A “brim”-like portion of the accumulated delamination does not govern the total delamination buckling behavior. The smallest diameter in the delamination governs the overall behavior.
8. Numerical simulations based on the delamination growth procedure with the same cohesive interface element can indicate the peak load in the compression and predict delamination propagation transversely to the load direction. Now, numerical experiments of multiply delaminated laminates are basically possible if the size of the model is small.

9. In-situ observation of OHC tests reveals that fiber micro-buckling in 0-layer starts early and it leads to delaminations between surrounding ± 45 layers. The rest of the mechanisms are different upon epoxy types, i.e., neat resin modulus and toughness.
10. Initial stages of the numerical simulations are conducted for OHC failure process. Qualitative explanation of the fiber micro-buckling is obtained. For a better correlation between numerical and experimental damage evolutions, further work will be needed.

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